

Pan Twardowski – a High Resolution Lunar Mineralogical Mapper. K. Natusiewicz, G. Wasilewski, T. Mróz and the HRLMM Team, Creotech Instruments S.A., Warsaw, Poland
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Introduction: The High Resolution Lunar Mineralogy Mapper (HRLMM) is a novel microsatellite mission developed by the European Space Agency and Creotech Instruments. The mission aims to provide high-resolution mineralogical mapping of the lunar surface, particularly in spectral bands and resolutions currently non-existent in public databases. This initiative addresses the growing demand for actionable lunar data to support scientific, commercial, and exploration objectives. The mission currently will enter Phase A of development.

Objectives: The mission's Measures of Effectiveness (MOEs) outline seven primary objectives. The mission cost must remain below 100 million EUR, with readiness for launch by the end of Q4 2028. Scientifically, the system aims to deliver telemetry and data enabling accurate identification and quantification of lunar mineral resources. The mission will achieve extensive coverage, mapping at least 90% of the lunar surface within one year of baseline service, explicitly including key regions such as Oceanus Procellarum, Mare Tranquillitatis, Mare Imbrium, and the permanently shadowed polar regions. High-quality spectral imaging data is required across multiple specific wavelength bands (0.35–2.5 μm , 8–14 μm , and precise infrared bands around 30–45 μm) at defined spectral resolutions to facilitate mineral mapping. Spatial resolutions must meet or exceed 2 meters (0.35–0.9 μm), 6 meters (0.9–14 μm), and 20 meters (30–45 μm), enabling detailed identification of minerals like ilmenite, apatite, and water ice.

Figure 1: Baseline S/C configuration

Mission baselines: The baseline spacecraft configuration builds upon Creotech's HyperSat microsatellite platform. The mission currently considers three launch options: a dedicated launch directly to Low Lunar Orbit, delivery to LLO as a secondary payload, or delivery to Lunar Transfer Orbit. Launches directly to LLO simplify spacecraft propulsion and operations, but such services have limited flight heritage, and the highest-rated providers, are also among the most expensive. A lunar impact

has been selected for spacecraft disposal due to manoeuvre simplicity and accuracy. Communication strategies include direct-to-Earth, relay satellite, or a combination of both; mixed communication, while more complex, provides greater bandwidth and redundancy critical for handling substantial in case of HRLMM scientific data volumes. The propulsion system's final design hinges on the chosen launch scenario and will be further analysed, considering chemical, electric, hybrid. Optical and thermal payloads are under consideration, with the combined payload consisting of LEO-flown VIS and SWIR telescopes, LEO-qualified LWIR telescopes and (currently) a low-TRL FIR optical telescope, recommended due to readiness and imaging quality, despite higher mass and power requirements. Achieving the desired lunar coverage within a reasonable mission duration requires careful balance among orbital altitude, data generation rate, and available communication bandwidth. Increasing altitude to 200 km preserves mission duration without excessive loss in spatial resolution, while improving image resolution or extending mission duration might require design adjustments to mitigate increased radiation exposure.

Name: The name Pan Twardowski refers to a legendary Polish sorcerer typically depicted as a noble either riding a rooster or standing on the Moon.

Figure 2: Pan Twardowski